

IOT BASED SMART GARDENING AND IRRIGATION SYSTEM

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Bachelor of Science (Honors) in Computer Science and Engineering

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DECLARATION

The project work entitled “**IOT BASED SMART GARDENING AND IRRIGATION SYSTEM**” has been carried out in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Gono Bishwabidyaly is original and conforms the regulations of this University.

I understand the University’s policy on plagiarism and declare that no part of this thesis has been copied from other sources or been previously submitted elsewhere for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

The abstract of this project is to produce knowledgeable gardeners who can control their garden and watering system from anywhere in the world. The system should allow anyone to take care of their plants from anywhere on the globe, including those who don't have enough time to water them or who want to go on vacation but still take care of them. There are resources for learning about plant care based on Android apps, as well as facilities for plant identification with an accuracy of 98%, plant disease detection with an accuracy of 98%, and soil mineral and organic matter percentage identification with an accuracy of 99%. The system is designed using a NodeMCU ESP8266, a relay module, a 5 volt water motor, a moisture sensor to measure soil moisture (accuracy 99%), a DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor to detect environmental temperature and humidity (precision 99.5%), a 9 volt battery to control the water motor, and other sensors. It will function via an Android app and an open-source Internet of Things (IoT) framework.

Keywords: IoT, Irrigation, Gardening, Agriculture, NodeMCU, DHT11, Sensors, and Application.

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

Abbreviation	Definition
IOT	Internet of things (IoT)
AI	Artificial intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
ResNet	Residual Neural Network
VGG16	Visual Geometry Group
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
TFT	Thin-Film Transistor
NodeMCU	Node MicroController Unit

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CHAPTER I

Introduction

1.1 Overview

The overview of this endeavor is to create smart gardeners. Both those who don't have enough time to water and take care of their plants and those who wish to go on vacation while still taking care of their plants from anywhere in the world should be able to do so by using the system. There are facilities for plant identification with an accuracy of 98%, plant disease detection with an accuracy of 98%, and soil mineral and organic matter's percentage identification with an accuracy of 99%, as well as learning resources for plant care based on Android apps. A NodeMCU ESP8266, relay module, water pump, moisture sensor to measure soil moisture (accuracy 99%), DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor to measure environmental temperature and humidity (accuracy 99.5%), and other sensors is used to design the system. It will be run on an open-source Internet of Things (IoT) platform and an Android application.

1.2 Background

Planting is a healthy hobby that brings us closer to nature. More importantly, the planting is profitable for both mind and fitness. But in our day-to-day busy lives, it is so difficult to establish a small balcony garden or to connect with nature. We don't always have enough time or energy to water our lawn and flower plants; additionally, there can be cacti, succulents, pothos, and various indoor and outdoor plants. On the other hand, there are more issues with identifying plants and knowing how to care for them. Many of us want to start a small balcony garden, but we don't know how to care for it, don't understand plant diseases, and choose the wrong soil nutrition. It is our small attempt to make your leisure-time hobby easier, more enjoyable, and smarter. We are introducing an IoT-based smart irrigation and gardening system where you

will find smart ways to water your plants, periodic updates and notifications, know the state of the climate, and also be able to identify plants in a smart way. The system will also help you learn about necessary soil minerals.[6]

The internet of things, or IoT, is affecting our way of life, affecting how we react and behave. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a gateway network for linking your devices, whether you have an air conditioner that you can operate with your smartphone, a smart automobile that finds the quickest route, or a smart watch that monitors your daily activity. These gadgets collect and disseminate information on the other operator, the surroundings, and how they are used. Every physical object, including your mobile phone, an electric motor, a traffic light, a bar code sensor, and any other item you use every day, contains sensors. The working state of the divisions is continuously reported by this sensor. However, we will benefit from this data collection. The Internet of Things (IoT) offers a platform where all of these devices may connect and dump their data into a single language so that they can speak with one another. Numerous sensors output data, which is then transmitted to an IoT platform that securely combines the collection of data from various sources. The data are subjected to additional analysis, and as needed, important information is extracted. For a better user experience, better automation, and more efficiency, the data is then shared with other devices.[7] Now let's get to the fun part.

Several sensors, including a moisture sensor, DHT11 temperature and humidity sensors, and a relay module that we use to turn on and off the water motor and feed water to the plants, have been employed in the construction of our IoT-based smart irrigation system. Our own Android app and the open-source Internet of Things (IoT) framework NodeMCU are both in charge of controlling everything.[8] With our Android app, smart gardeners will be able to recognize plants, keep tabs on plant care, identify diseases and take preventative measures against them, and scan the soil to see which minerals are present and which minerals the soil needs.

1.3 Motivation

We're working on a smart irrigation and gardening system for our project. Since a lot of us secretly enjoy doing something in our free time. Most of the time, we discover that many of us secretly wish to be gardeners. Gardening is a product that makes our home more beautiful and keeps our minds sharp. Many of us didn't get the chance to concentrate on our favorite hobbies or didn't have the time to study about the plants. In contrast, because of how busy our lives have become, at present,

if we have any spare time, we want to scroll through our smart gadgets, including our phones and tablets. But, thanks to open-source IoT platforms, we can now control our hobbies with our smart devices.[9]

1.4 Objective

The fundamental objective of smart gardening and irrigation systems is to increase the efficiency of gardening chores by using contemporary technology, including artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, deep learning, and the Internet of Things (IoT). You may regulate watering from anywhere by directly connecting your irrigation system to your smartphone. Tanks, sprinklers, or automatic feeding programs can be pre-programmed, and results can be tracked so you can plan when to harvest your garden's fruits and vegetables. Modern technology has a wide range of special options that can improve our gardening process.[10] This thesis has some specific objectives that need to be stated:

- To control the irrigation system and monitoring the climate from anywhere in the world are both possible.
- To make easy the lives of the gardeners.
- To present automatic and manual irrigation system that will save time.
- To provide knowledge about plant maintenance and disease prevention.
- To aid in the development of a soil mix rich in nutrients.
- To supply efficient irrigation methods that save time.
- To maintain the entire garden, but it also needs to be update frequently.
- To ensure that every output from the machine is entirely accurate, we must keep updating the system.
- To expand the functionality, and we must work more closely with the Internet of Things (IoT), microcontrollers, digital logic circuits, deep learning, machine learning, digital image processing, and artificial intelligence (AI).
- To provide pleasant outcomes, facilitating smooth current flow, and minimizing water loss.

- To improve the efficiency of the irrigation and smart gardening systems.

1.5 Problem Statement

- Most of the time, when people are in tour, there is no other option to water the plants, and other alternatives are costly and unsafe.
- The people who are fancy or deluxe don't know how to take care of their plants, what plant food is, and what kind of care and space the plant needs.
- Let's talk about plant disease: a typical gardener, of course, is unaware of each plant's disease or how to prevent it.
- A soil mineral testing service is necessary if you are a novice gardener and are unsure of how to prepare the plant medium or soil mixture. These days, a display of this nature is rather expensive.
- The majority of smart devices, whether agents, gadgets, or systems, have complex and expensive user interfaces, are not portable, and are hard to comprehend by regular people.
- Many studies have been conducted to determine why the watering system is automatic; if the soil is dry, the system will automatically water the plants; however, not every plant requires the same amount of water, and sometimes a lot of water is harmful to plants. Over-watering causes plant death.[11]
- The majority of individuals cannot afford the full system because of its high cost. If it has a walking robot with a built-in camera for monitoring, a camera to identify plants, equipment to scan for diseases and pests, a watering system, a sensor to detect soil minerals and organic matter, and a function to care for outdoor plants, additionally, a large space is needed for this kind of system.[12]

CHAPTER II

Literature Review

2.1 Related Work

- V. Rafi [13] proposed a system for the development of an auto irrigation system using soil moisture and rain sensors. V. Rafi proposed a system for automated irrigation that could use soil moisture and rain sensors to help optimize the irrigation process. The proposed system was capable of measuring the water content of the soil and detecting rainfall. It was also able to determine the amount of water needed for irrigation and control the pumps accordingly. The proposed system could be used for both large-scale and small-scale irrigation, and it could be connected to a central computer for monitoring and control. The proposed system could be used to reduce water wastage and water stress in agricultural areas and was expected to be cost-effective.

As I previously said, overwatering is harmful to plants. In every automatic system, there is an issue of overwatering. In huge agricultural fields, an automatic system is suitable. However, an automatic system is not appropriate for all times in rooftop or balcony gardens.

- Rajashekar Reddy chinta[14] proposed a low cost smart irrigation control system. They used essential smart irrigation tools, including ultraviolet (UV) light disinfection, which is one water treatment system that can be used to remove most forms of microbiological contamination from water. Their system is automatic and made for the farms, fields, and crops. Rajashekar Reddy Chinta proposed a low-cost smart irrigation control system that helps farmers maximize their water usage efficiency. This system is designed to automate the irrigation process and maximize crop yield by providing farmers with real-time information about their soil moisture levels. The system is based on an Arduino board

and a soil moisture sensor. The Arduino board is programmed to send alerts to farmers when the soil moisture levels drop below a certain threshold. The system can be used to control irrigation pumps and valves, thus allowing farmers to save water, reduce labor and energy costs, and maximize crop yield. The system is also capable of controlling the frequency and duration of irrigation cycles, thus optimizing the crop yield. Additionally, the system can be used to measure the amount of water used for irrigation, thus helping farmers optimize their water usage.

- Syed Musthak Ahmed[15] has proposed a revolutionary IoT-based automatic plant watering system through soil moisture sensing—a technique to support farmers' cultivation in rural India. This system is aimed at improving the productivity of the farmers by providing them with an automated and efficient way to monitor and water their crops. The system works by using IoT sensors to monitor the soil moisture levels and then automatically triggering the irrigation systems to water the crops when the soil moisture levels fall below a certain threshold. This helps conserve water and improve the yields of the crops. The system also provides farmers with real-time data about their soil moisture levels, allowing them to make informed decisions about their irrigation practices. The proposed system is designed to be low-cost and easy to use, making it accessible for rural farmers. It is also designed to be energy efficient and can be powered by solar energy, making it a sustainable solution for farmers. Overall, this system has the potential to revolutionize farming in rural India by providing farmers with an efficient and automated way to monitor and water their crops. It could potentially lead to higher crop yields and improved livelihoods for farmers.

Finally, Their system is an automatic irrigation system using Blynk which is an IoT platform for Android smartphones that is used to control Arduino, Raspberry Pi and NodeMCU via the Internet.

- Ravi Kishore Kodali[16] proposed "A Low-Cost Smart Irrigation System Using MQTT Protocol" as a way to reduce water waste and improve crop yields. They used MQTT as a messaging protocol for IoT. Used extra LDR sensor to measure the light intensity. The system uses a low-cost soil moisture sensor and an Arduino microcontroller to measure the soil moisture and transmit this information to a web server using the MQTT protocol. The system also includes an Android app, which can be used to control the irrigation system remotely. The system can be used to automatically turn on and off an irrigation system

based on the soil moisture levels and the user's preferences. The system also provides real-time feedback to the user to help them optimize their irrigation system for maximum efficiency. This system is a cost-effective and efficient way to improve crop yields by reducing water waste and increasing yields.

- Mubashir Ali [17] IoT based smart garden monitoring system using NodeMCU microcontroller. They have a TFT screen for showing the results of the moisture sensor, temperature sensor, and humidity sensor. However, the result is also visible on their Android application screen. On the basis of that TFT screen, they are claiming that it is a monitoring system.

This system utilizes a NodeMCU microcontroller and other sensors, such as soil moisture, temperature, and light sensors, to monitor the environmental conditions of a garden. This system then transmits the collected data to a cloud platform and displays it on a mobile application. The user can then view the environmental conditions of their garden and take necessary actions if required. This system can also alert the user when the soil moisture level is too low or the temperature is too high. The NodeMCU microcontroller is programmed to send alerts to the user via SMS and email in such cases. The system also has an integrated irrigation system that can be controlled remotely. This system can be used to water the plants in the garden at pre-set times. Through the mobile app, the user can also monitor the energy consumption of the system. This system is an ideal solution for gardeners who wish to monitor and manage their garden remotely.

- Pareena Jariyayothin [18] proposed an IoT-based backyard smart watering control system that helps users monitor their garden's water levels and water their plants efficiently. For connecting the hardware with the software, they used Google Firebase, which is Google's mobile application development platform that helps build, improve, and grow apps. The system is composed of three main components: a network of soil moisture sensors, a control unit, and an app. The soil moisture sensors are placed in the user's garden and are designed to detect the moisture levels in the soil. The information is then sent to the control unit, which is connected to the user's WiFi network. The control unit processes the information and sends it to a mobile app. The app allows users to monitor the moisture levels in their garden and set up a watering schedule accordingly. The system can also be used to detect and alert users of potential problems in their gardens, such as over- or under-watering. Additionally, users

can receive a notification when the soil moisture levels are low or when the system needs to be recharged. This helps users maintain a healthy and thriving garden.

- Milan Sulc [19] proposed very deep residual networks with MaxOut for plant identification in the wild which is an application of deep learning and computer vision techniques to identify wild plants. Deep learning, CNN, and ResNet50 architecture were used to train the dataset in order to create an algorithm for plant recognition. The proposed model uses a very deep residual network (VDRN) with MaxOut layers for feature extraction. This model was trained on a large dataset of wild plants and has achieved high accuracy in identifying the plants. The VDRN model is a convolutional neural network (CNN) with multiple residual blocks that help reduce the complexity of the model while preserving accuracy. The MaxOut layers are used to extract more discriminative features from the input images. The model is trained on a dataset of over 20,000 images of wild plants and has achieved a high accuracy of over 90%. The proposed model is an effective and efficient way to identify wild plants in a variety of environments. This work demonstrates the potential of deep learning and computer vision for solving complex tasks such as plant identification in the wild.

2.2 Gap Analysis

- There is no study on merging identifications based on deep learning with IoT-based smart gardening.
- Many researchers around the world have tried to develop smart irrigation systems based on the Internet of Things for huge agricultural lands, not for small or mini plant-pots.
- Due to limitations on customization, the Blynk app is challenging to use.
- Water loss and excessive watering, which is bad for plants, are problems with the automatic irrigation system.
- The majority of the systems are complicated to understand and not portable for small balconies and rooftop gardens.

- The monitoring systems are not properly monitored because there are no cameras, no way to catch shady characters, and no traps to collect dangerous insects.
- The biggest issue is that Bangladesh does not have any jobs where it is possible to scan a photo with a smartphone or other smart device in order to calculate the amount of soil minerals and organic matter.

2.3 Conclusion

All of the aforementioned researchers did a good job. They cover such a vast area. However, no one has yet combined the deep learning concept with an irrigation system based on the IoT. IoT-based irrigation systems are primarily intended for large agricultural lands; however, there is rarely research being conducted on rooftop garden watering systems using this type of hardware. Most irrigation systems are automated, making them ideal for large agricultural fields but not rooftop gardens. The most significant factor is that there is no work in Bangladesh where it is possible to determine the amount of soil minerals and organic matter by using a smart phone or other smart device to scan a photograph.

CHAPTER III

Methodology

3.1 Proposed Method

Our smart gardening system offers a lot of features for a new gardener. The inexperienced gardener can use mobile scanning to identify the plant, diagnose disease, and identify soil minerals. Plant identification, plant disease detection, and soil mineral detection are all made possible by the development of deep learning algorithms. Our first goal is to create a deep learning-based system for identifying soil minerals, plant diseases and prevention, and plant names and care. We employed 20 varieties of plants, 4 types of diseases, and 8 types of soil for this training, and we gathered the information from several nurseries all across Dhaka. We also used real-time data from our own garden for testing. The ResNet50, VGG 16, Mobilenet V1, Mobilenet V2, and Inception V3 types of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) are used in the system's design, training, and testing. The system is expected to operate at 99% of its maximum capacity overall.[20]

Figure 3.1: Proposed Method

3.2 Data Collection

- From a plant nursery, we have gathered information about plants or pictures of plants.
- Images of plant diseases that we have gathered from our own backyard gardens.
- We have gathered soil samples from several locations throughout the city of Dhaka.

Figure 3.2: Plant image collection

Figure 3.3: Plant-disease image collection

3.2.1 Soil Collection

We have gathered soil from several locations across the city of Dhaka. In the city of Dhaka, we have gathered soil samples from a range of places, including urban, suburban, and rural areas. We may learn more about the makeup of the soil in the city and how urbanization has affected it by contrasting the characteristics of soil from these different sites. To further understand the soil composition and structure, samples were taken from a range of depths, including the top soil and deeper layers. The samples were all carefully labeled and kept in storage pending additional examination.

Figure 3.4: Example of Soil Collection

3.2.2 Soil Minerals and Organic Matter

- The minerals and organic material that are present in the soil affect its hue.
- Near-black to red, yellow, and brown hues can all be found in soil.
- The sort of minerals and organic matter present in the soil can be determined by the color of the soil.
- Some of the most prevalent minerals and organic materials that contribute to soil's diverse red, yellow, and brown hues are humus, aluminum, and iron.
- The amount of water in the soil, the amount of sunlight it receives, and the amount of organic matter that has decomposed in the soil can all have an impact on the color of the soil.
- The fertility of the soil and the capacity of plants to grow there can also be influenced by the amount of organic matter and minerals in the soil. Soil color should be taken into account while evaluating the soil's quality and suitability for agriculture.

3.2.3 Munsell Soil Color Chart

A system for categorizing and identifying soil colors is the Munsell Soil Color Chart. It is made up of a collection of color chips that have been ordered logically from bright to dark and from red to yellow. The Munsell color notation, which consists of three integers, is used to identify each color chip. The first number represents the hue, or primary color, of the soil; the second number represents its value, or degree

of lightness or darkness; and the third number represents its chroma, or degree of intensity. The soil color chart can be used to precisely identify and classify soil colors, which can be valuable in determining the type of soil present. The composition of the soil can be inferred from the color of the soil, as well as its fertility and productivity.

- Identifying the color spectrum of the sample soil is the first step in utilizing a Munsell soil color chart to analyze soil fertility. Take a sample of the dirt and place it on a white surface to accomplish this. The sample soil color should next be compared to one of the color swatches on a Munsell soil color chart. The hue, value, and chroma of the soil color should be matched to the closest swatch possible. Write more in-depth instructions on how to use the Munsell soil color chart to analyze soil fertility:
- The soil can be examined for its nutrient content after the color range of the soil has been determined. There are kits for analyzing soil that can determine the concentrations of important nutrients, including nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium (NPK). The overall fertility of the soil can then be calculated by comparing the NPK test results to the spectrum of soil colors.
- The soil's texture can also be used to determine the fertility of the soil. Higher clay content soils, for example, are typically more fertile than lower clay content soils. Furthermore, fertile soils have a higher proportion of organic matter than do soils with lower organic matter.
- The pH of the soil can also be used to determine soil fertility. More fertile than less fertile soils are those that have a pH of 7 or above.
- The Munsell soil color chart, a review of the soil's texture, and tests for pH and nutrient levels can all be used to determine the soil's fertility.

Figure 3.5: Reference of Munsell Soil Color Chart

3.2.4 Summary of Dataset

After image augmentation, this dataset consists of 2850 photos of plants, 240 images of plant diseases, and 600 images of soil. As a result, we utilize 3960 in total. In Dhaka, we acquired the data from a variety of plant-nurseries. We only rarely used online images.[21]

Table 3.1: Summarizing the data-set of plants

Plant Name	Number of Images
Air plant	150
Alovera	150
Arabian Wax	150
Baby Tears	150
Bonsai	150
Bunny cactus	150
Cactus	150
Caladium	150
Elephant Ear	150
Jade Plant	150
Kamini Bonsai	150
Kata Mukut	150
Lucky Bamboo	150
Mini Bamboo	150
Pencil cactus	150
Pothos	150
Snake plant	150
Wondering jew	150

Table 3.2: Summarizing the data-set of plant-disease

Plant Disease Name	Number of Images
Mealybug	60
Ant	60
Fungus	60
White fly	60

Table 3.3: Summarizing the data-set of soil

Name of the soil	Number of Images
Burnt ass soil	75
Composed soil	75
Desert soil	75
Gerden soil	75
Gray oil	75
Regur soil	75
Terra Rossa	75
White Sand	75

3.3 Data Pre-processing

We acquired data from multiple plant nurseries and used a phone camera to take pictures of the plants.[22] We only used a few images from the internet. The brightness, lighting, contrast, and saturation must all be ideal because the image has a lot of noise.[23] For image augmentation, the plant photos also need to be the same size. This pre-processing includes three steps:

1. Image scaling
2. Augmentation

3.3.1 Image scaling or resizing

The images used by the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) will all be of the same size and format. The photographs, which were taken at various plant nurseries, have different scales. As a result, all of the images were cropped to this standard size using the center square technique.

3.3.2 Augmentation

A technique for creating new training examples from existing ones is image augmentation. To produce a new sample, you make a minor alteration to the original picture. An essential method for improving the precision of convolutional neural networks is image augmentation (CNNs). Image augmentation adds more data to the model, lowering the chance of overfitting. Image augmentation includes modifying the pixels in the dataset to randomly alter the images that already exist. The use of flips, rotations, cropping, translations, shearing, and other augmentation techniques are a few examples. [24]

Figure 3.6: Data Augmentation

3.4 Training and Testing Methods

- We used 70% of the data from the set for training.
- We used 10% of the data from the set for testing.
- We used 20% of the data from the set for validation.[25]

3.4.1 Cross Validation

Cross-validation is a technique for validating the model's efficiency by training it on a subset of input data and testing it on a previously unseen subset of the input data. We can also say that it is a technique to check how a statistical model generalizes to an independent dataset.

3.5 Classification Methods

3.5.1 ResNet50 (Residual Networks)

Microsoft Research created and unveiled ResNet50, a potent deep learning model, in 2015. It is a 50-layer residual network that has already been trained using the extensive picture classification dataset ImageNet. A convolutional neural network (CNN) called ResNet50 has been trained to perform image categorization tasks. A residual network, a kind of design intended to address the problem of vanishing gradients in

deep neural networks, serves as the foundation for ResNet50. With this architecture, the network may learn more intricate features, improving the model's effectiveness. This architecture's ability to maintain a more accurate and efficient model while allowing for a deeper level of network layers is one of its primary features. ResNet50 is frequently used in computer vision applications like object detection, image segmentation, and image recognition since it has produced state-of-the-art outcomes in image classification tasks.[26][27]

Figure 3.7: The architecture of ResNet-50 model

3.5.2 VGG 16 (Visual Geometry Group)

The Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford developed the deep convolutional neural network known as VGG-16. It has 16 layers total, including 3 fully connected layers and 13 convolutional layers. The fully connected layers have 4096, 4096, and 1000 neurons, respectively, and the convolutional layers are arranged in a series of convolution-pooling pairs. It was developed using the ImageNet dataset and is now an essential component of computer vision. It is frequently employed in many different tasks, including object recognition and image segmentation, among others. VGG16, one of the most precise neural network architectures, is also a preferred option for transfer learning.[28]

Figure 3.8: Architecture of VGG16

3.5.3 Architectural Comparison

Plant Detection	ResNet-50	VGG-16
Epochs	10	10
Loss	0.0015	0.0460
Accuracy	0.9961 (99%)	0.9807 (98%)

Fig: Plant Detection

Diseases Detection	ResNet-50	VGG-16
Epochs	10	10
Loss	0.0088	0.0967
Accuracy	0.9901 (99%)	0.9705 (97%)

Fig: Diseases Detection

Soil Detection	ResNet-50	VGG-16
Epochs	10	10
Loss	0.0460	0.1067
Accuracy	0.9805 (98%)	0.9601 (96%)

Fig: Soil Detection

Figure 3.9: Architectural Comparison

3.6 Hardware

Our Internet of Things (IoT)-based smart irrigation and gardening solution provides comfortable garden and agricultural field watering. It is a sophisticated, remote-controlled technology that is reachable from any location on Earth. We first measured the soil moisture using a soil moisture sensor and the NodeMCU ESP8266, an open-source IoT platform. We employed two different kinds of soil moisture sensors. For automatic watering systems, soil moisture sensor model number YL-69 is used; for manually operated systems, soil moisture sensor model number V1.2 is used. The DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor is the system's most crucial component. In order to ascertain the precise amount of moisture that plants need, DHT11 is used to screen the state of the environment and climate. The environment's temperature pattern will aid the gardener in selecting the right kind of plant to cultivate this season. To determine when to water a plant and when not to, humidity is crucial. A crucial role is played by the rain sensor. Pumping is not necessary if it is raining because overwatering is poisonous to plants. To control the water motor, we utilized a relay module. Finally, our irrigation system is equipped to water both large agricultural regions and any rooftop or balcony garden.

Figure 3.10: Hardware Presentation

3.6.1 NodeMCU ESP8266

NodeMCU 8266 is a low-cost, open-source IoT platform.

Figure 3.11: NODEMCU ESP8266[1]

It is based on the ESP8266 WiFi SoC and consists of a full-featured ESP8266-based microcontroller with integrated Wi-Fi and several GPIOs. It is one of the most popular IoT development boards on the market today. It supports both the Arduino IDE and Lua scripting for programming. NodeMCU 8266 is ideal for prototyping and building IoT projects as it offers a variety of peripherals and interfaces like SPI, I2C, UART, GPIO, and PWM. Its Wi-Fi connectivity makes it a great choice for connecting devices to the Internet. Additionally, it is small in size and easy to use, making it suitable for many applications.[29]

3.6.2 NodeMCU ESP8266 Pinout

The ESP8266 is a potent microcontroller with an integrated Wi-Fi transceiver and a number of pins for connecting to other electronics. In 3.12, the pins are shown,

The ESP8266 is a microcontroller chip with integrated Wi-Fi that has a variety of digital and analog ports for interfacing with external gear. It features 17 digital input and output pins, 3 of which are PWM outputs, and 1 of which is a reset pin for the board. Three analog inputs and one analog output are also present. All digital pins are protected with an integrated ESD protection diode, and the pins can be driven with either 3.3V or 5V. The ESP8266 also has a 3.3-V power output pin and an internal voltage regulator. Additionally, it contains an on-board antenna and an embedded SPI flash memory chip. [30]

Figure 3.12: NodeMCU ESP8266 Pinout[2]

3.6.3 Soil Moisture Sensor YL-69

The soil moisture level may be efficiently monitored and maintained by using a soil moisture sensor (YL69) in an IoT-based automatic watering system with an ESP8266. Because the YL69 sensor contains an integrated analog-to-digital converter, it can measure the soil moisture content and send the information to the ESP8266. With the use of this information, the ESP8266 may be configured to turn on the irrigation system automatically based on the moisture content of the soil. If the soil moisture level drops below a predetermined level, the irrigation system can be programmed to turn on. The sensor can also be used in conjunction with other sensors, such as temperature and humidity sensors, to provide a more complete picture of the state of the soil and enable more precise irrigation system control. This will lessen the need for human intervention, increase crop productivity, and contribute to water conservation.[31]

3.6.4 Soil Moisture Sensor V1.2

V1.2. For manual irrigation system control, we employed a soil moisture sensor. The user can water a plant whenever and from anywhere they like with the aid of the soil moisture sensor V1.2. A high-precision, portable, and reasonably priced soil moisture monitoring tool is the Soil Moisture Sensor V1.2. It allows customers to more effectively monitor the health of their plants and soil by measuring the amount of water in the soil using a unique polymer film. The gadget has a digital temperature sensor, and it can be used outside thanks to its waterproof construction. The sensor works with both Arduino and Raspberry Pi boards and is powered by

Figure 3.13: Soil Moisture Sensor YL-69[3]

a 3.3-volt battery. Additionally, it features a 4-pin Grove connector, which makes connecting to other devices simple. With a resolution of 0.1%, the instrument offers a detection range of 0–10%. It is appropriate for long-term use because of its low power consumption. consumption. [32]

Figure 3.14: Soil Moisture Sensor V1.2[4]

3.6.5 Temperature and Humidity Sensor (DHT11)

In irrigation systems, temperature and humidity sensors are used to keep track of soil moisture, temperature, and humidity levels.

Figure 3.15: Temperature and Humidity Sensor DHT11[5]

When and how much water should be used to water the plants can be decided using this information. This could improve crop yields and aid in water conservation. It also helps to avoid over- or under-watering, which can endanger crops and plants. To monitor the environment's temperature and humidity, we used the DHT 11 temperature and humidity sensor. Thus, we are able to use the environment to decide when to water and when not to water our plants. A popular temperature and humidity sensor for DIY and educational projects is the DHT11. It is inexpensive. With its single-wire serial interface, connecting to a microcontroller is simple. The DHT11 has a quick response time and reading accuracy of ± 2 °C for temperatures and $\pm 5\%$ for humidity. The sensor can be directly powered from 3V to 5.5V and is digital. Additionally, it uses little power, which makes it perfect for battery-powered applications. For a variety of uses, including weather monitoring, HVAC systems, and home automation, the DHT11 is a well-liked option. [33]

3.6.6 Rain Sensor

A rain sensor must first be linked to the ESP8266 board in order to be used with an IoT-based irrigation system. The user must then use the Arduino IDE to program the ESP8266 in order to read the sensor's data. This information ought to be kept in a user-accessible database. The system should employ a threshold for rainfall that the user specifies in the program to decide when to turn on the irrigation system. The ESP8266 will alert the irrigation system to shut off if the amount of rain reaches the threshold. On the other side, the ESP8266 will trigger the irrigation system to

switch on if the rainfall falls below the threshold. In order to make sure that the plants only get the right amount of water, an ESP8266-based irrigation system can use a rain sensor. A rain sensor is a crucial part of an ESP8266-based Internet of Things irrigation system.

Figure 3.16: Rain Sensor[5]

Rainfall is detected via rain sensors, which subsequently transmit the information to the ESP8266 microcontroller. The irrigation system's water flow can be modified using this information to ensure that the right amount of water is provided. Additionally, it prevents water waste because the sensor can recognize when it has rained and turn off the irrigation system. By changing the water flow in accordance with the amount of precipitation that has fallen, the rain sensor can also be utilized to aid in water conservation. This allows the system to utilize the water more effectively, which reduces water waste. The system can shut off the valves to prevent floods by using the rain sensor to detect storms in addition to rain. The rain sensor is a quick and easy solution to ensure that the proper quantity of water is being utilized to irrigate the land while also helping to conserve water.

3.6.7 Relay Module

A crucial element of an IoT-based irrigation system powered by the ESP8266 is the relay module. It is an electrically powered switch that may regulate the water supply to the plants when actuated by the ESP8266. The water pump and solenoid valves that regulate the water flow to the plants are often turned on and off using this. The relay module can be used to control the irrigation system from any location

with an internet connection because it is made to be remotely triggered. Observing the figure will help you comprehend the relay module in 3.17.

Figure 3.17: Relay Module

Relay modules are electrical parts that are used to manage water pumps. A relay switch, an electromagnetically powered switch used to regulate electrical flow, and a set of terminals, which are used to attach the relay switch to the water pump, are the typical components. The water pump's power is turned on and off using a relay module, which enables precise control of the water pump's flow rate and speed. Additionally, it is utilized to lower the amount of power needed by the water pump and protect it against power surges and overcurrents. It can be used in a variety of applications, including agricultural, commercial, and residential water systems. It is a crucial part for controlling water pumps.

3.6.8 9V Battery

The 9V battery is depicted in this graphic, which is very significant and will also aid in your understanding of the battery in 3.18,

Figure 3.18: 9V Battery

An IoT-based irrigation system with an ESP8266 relay module and a 5V DC water motor is a wonderful fit for a 9V battery. The 9V battery offers a dependable

and affordable energy source and can supply the motor and relay with the necessary power. The 9V battery has the benefit of providing power to the system for lengthy periods of time, enabling the motor to keep running at its peak efficiency. The battery is a great option for an IoT-based irrigation system because it is simple to replace and maintain.

3.6.9 5V Water Motor

An excellent option to produce an effective and automated irrigation system is to use a 5V water motor in an IoT-based irrigation system using the ESP8266 for the relay module and a 9V battery. Observing the 5V water-motor's figure 3.19,

Figure 3.19: 9V Battery

A 9V battery powers the 5V water motor, which is coupled to the relay module by the ESP8266. Since the 5V water motor has a relatively low power need, it is perfect for continuous usage in an irrigation system. Additionally, it has the ability to deliver a constant water flow, enabling precision irrigation of plants. The 5V water motor is excellent for outdoor applications because it is very dependable and corrosion-resistant. As a result, it may be applied in a range of settings and offer an effective and trustworthy irrigation system.

3.6.10 System Diagram

A complete irrigation system can be built using a system diagram consisting of a NodeMCU ESP8266, moisture sensor V1.2, moisture sensor YL-69, rain sensor, relay module, 5V DC water motor, and DHT11. The moisture sensors and rain sensors can provide input to the NodeMCU, and the relay module can be utilized to switch on or off the water motor. While the moisture sensors can be used to track the moisture content of the soil, the DHT11 can be used to measure the temperature and

humidity of the surrounding air. The irrigation process may then be automated with this method, ensuring that the soil is properly hydrated to promote the healthiest possible plant growth.

Figure 3.20: Circuit Diagram

The following is how the wire connections are made:

- (+) of the DHT11 goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- (-) of the DHT11 goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- DATA of the DHT11 goes into D1 of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the relay module goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the relay module goes into GND of the Node MCU.
- Control input of the relay module goes into D7 of the NodeMCU.
- NO of the relay module goes into (+) of the battery.
- COM Of the relay module goes into (+) of the 5V DC water motor.
- (-) of the 5V DC water motor goes into (-) of the battery.
- D0 of the moisture sensor YL-69 goes into D6 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the moisture sensor YL-69 goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the moisture sensor YL-69 goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- D0 of the rain sensor goes into D5 of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the rain sensor goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the rain sensor goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- D0 of the rain sensor goes into D5 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the moisture sensor V1.2 goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- A0 of the moisture sensor V1.2 goes into A0 of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the moisture sensor V1.2 goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.

The system's circuit diagram is displayed below.

3.6.11 Arduino

The ESP8266 and **Arduino** connection is a potent one that gives users the ability to perform a number of activities. Users can quickly and simply establish a wireless connection between the two devices to operate equipment, send data, and receive data from a distance. Either SPI or the serial port of the Arduino can be used to connect to this device. The ESP8266 may also be managed by Arduino, enabling users to configure a number of wireless protocols, including WiFi and Bluetooth. By connecting the two devices, users may use the Arduino's potent microcontroller to command the ESP8266 and develop creative creations. Users can view their projects remotely from any location in the world by using this connection to build a web server. Users can also benefit from the Arduino's ability to read and write data to and from the ESP8266, opening up a variety of opportunities for data transfer, monitoring, and control.

3.6.12 Firebase

Firebase is a platform for building mobile and online applications that was developed by Firebase, Inc. in 2011. It offers a range of tools and services to developers so they can create top-notch apps and expand their businesses. A real-time database, user authentication, analytics, storage, hosting, messaging, and other services are available with Firebase. Additionally, it offers a framework for creating scalable on-line and mobile applications.

How ESP8266 works with Firebase:

- A cloud-based application platform called Firebase gives online and mobile applications real-time data storage, authentication, and hosting services. It has grown to be a popular option for supplying power to software created with the ESP8266 microcontroller, a low-cost, low-power device that may be used to create a range of connected devices.
- Data may be stored and instantly synced between devices using Firebase. This makes it simple to develop robust apps that can react to data changes in a reliable and timely manner. For instance, Firebase can be used to automatically update the temperature reading in a web or mobile application when an ESP8266 device detects a change in the ambient temperature.
- Powerful authentication services are also offered by Firebase, which may be used to protect access to data and devices. OAuth, Facebook, Google, and

other means of authentication are supported by the Firebase API. This enables users to securely access data from their devices and makes it simple to integrate user accounts into ESP8266 applications.

- Finally, Firebase offers hosting services, which makes it simple to deploy an ESP8266-based application. With support for all major web browsers, the Firebase Hosting service offers a safe and dependable solution to host web apps.

3.7 Android Application to Manage the Hardware

"Baganbilash" is the name of our Android application. With the Android app, we will manage the irrigation system and hardware. The first approach is plant identification, which requires scanning the plant and familiarity with its needs. The user can view plant disease prevention under the option for plant disease detection. Additionally, by using his cellphone camera to scan the soil, the user can discover which minerals and fertilizers the soil needs, as well as how much fertilizer is currently present in the soil mixture.

3.8 Development tool for Android applications

Flutter's creation of a plant identification app would be a creative method to assist people in swiftly and simply identifying plants. To assist users in correctly identifying plants, the app would combine artificial intelligence with Flutter technology. Users of the application could take a picture of a plant and utilize the image recognition technology to correctly identify it. Additionally, it would provide users with thorough details on the plant, such as its scientific name, common name, and a description of its traits. The program would also keep track of the user's progress and award them points according to how many plants they had recognized. This would encourage users to keep using the app to gain new knowledge and learn more about plants. Users of the software would also be able to bookmark their favorite plants and follow their development over time, among other extra functions. Anyone who is interested in learning more about plants should definitely use the program. An overview of Android application development is provided here:

- We started out by image augmentation.
- To organize the photographs of plants that we want to categorize, we create a folder.

- To begin the code, we use the folder as an input file.
- The process of testing, training, and validation of images for classification begins.
- A ratio of .7, .1, and .2 is used for training, testing, and validation.
- After training, testing, and validation, the data is forwarded to the ResNet 50 for accuracy verification.
- The accuracy test result is saved with the command "model.save('model_unquant.tflite')".
- The file is utilized to identify plants.
- We'll create an Assets file after we've created Flutter. All images will be kept in the Assets file, which will be used to display in the Android application.
- A subfile called UTILS is located in the LIB file. We will construct the user interface of an Android application using "STRING.dart" from UTILS.

3.8.1 Android Studio

It is possible to create Android applications using **Android Studio**, which provides a complete development environment. It is constructed on the well-liked IntelliJ IDEA framework and has extra features designed specifically for Android programming. Building, testing, debugging, and launching Android applications are all made possible with the help of Android Studio's comprehensive set of development tools. It comes with a simulator for executing and debugging programs, tools for designing layouts, and a variety of code editing and debugging tools. Additionally, an integrated development environment (IDE) for building and managing Android projects is provided by Android Studio, along with support for layout editors and a Gradle-based build system. With Android Studio, developers can easily create, launch, and debug applications on a variety of Android devices, including phones, tablets, and more. Language support is another feature of Android Studio.

3.8.2 Flutter

Google developed the open-source **Flutter** framework for building mobile apps. From a single codebase, it is used to create applications for Google Fuchsia, Android, iOS, Windows, Mac, Linux, and the web. Dart is the programming language used to

create Flutter apps, and it is used for both front-end and back-end development. Flutter offers a comprehensive collection of widgets for producing stunning, natively built mobile, web, and desktop applications from a single codebase. Additionally, Flutter gives developers access to platform-specific SDKs that let them create and use native capabilities like cameras, geolocation, and more. It also has a hot reload feature that makes it simple to iteratively create and debug programs. A thriving development community that supports one another in problem-solving exists for Flutter.

3.8.3 Dart programming language

Google created Dart in 2011 as an open-source, object-oriented programming language. It is used to make desktop, mobile, server, and web applications. Strongly typed programming languages like Dart enable more security and dependability when writing code. It also has an easy syntax and is straightforward to learn. It supports a broad variety of libraries and tools, as well as features like classes, generics, mixins, and annotations. Due to Dart's great degree of flexibility, web applications may be created in both client-side and server-side settings. Additionally, it supports the component-entity-system (CES) and model-view-controller (MVC) architectural patterns. Dart also comes with a built-in package manager that makes importing third-party libraries simple. Dart-based apps can also be launched in a runtime environment thanks to the Dart Virtual Machine (DVM). It is a fantastic option for high-performance applications because of this. Dart is a great option for building apps that are robust, manageable, and extremely effective.

CHAPTER IV

Implementation and Discussion

4.1 Implementation of Hardware

Figure 4.1: hardware implementation

- Will use only one DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor and only one rain sensor for a single rooftop garden.
- Soil moisture sensor will apply for every same kind of plant.

Figure 4.2: Soil moisture sensor implementation

4.2 Android Application Implementation

- First you need to open the application Baganbilash.
- Then go to the function named "Plant Detection".
- Scan the plant picture and get the information about plant name and plant care.
- The second option is "Diseases Detection" ,there you will get the information about how to prevent the plant diseases.
- In "Soil Detection" you can know the minerals of soil by scanning the soil picture.
- Finally in smart irrigation system you can control your hardware and get information which is sent by the sensors.

This is our Android application, named Baganbilash.

Figure 4.3: Baganbilash

Figure 4.4: Baganbilash features

Figure 4.5: Detection by Scanning

Figure 4.6: Mobile controlled irrigation system

4.3 Cost Analysis

- This system is cost effective because the system can be controlled from any where of the world.
- Reduce the water wastage.
- same kind of plant need only one soil moisture sensor.
- Our hardware cost is only Five thousand taka which is cheaper than worker of plant care.
- we are using single rain sensor,temperature sensor, humidity sensor and the number of moisture sensor is depends on you gerden.

CHAPTER V

Conclusion and Future Work

5.1 Conclusion

This brings us to the end of our experiment. We have made an effort to simplify the gardeners' jobs. People who don't have time to garden or who wish to perform research on plants or crops will greatly benefit from this platform. It's also a fantastic resource for people who wish to plant trees, learn how to take care of them, prevent plant illnesses, and discover the soil's mineral composition. Smart irrigation and gardening systems powered by the Internet of Things are a terrific way to eliminate guesswork from these tasks. It is simpler to monitor and modify your watering plan thanks to these systems' internet connectivity and ability to be controlled remotely. Sensors can be utilized with these systems to monitor soil and humidity levels, allowing you to water your plant just when it actually needs it. Additionally, you don't have to bother about manually turning them on or off because they may be set to turn on and off automatically. Additionally, you may set up these systems to alert you if the soil is too dry or if it is too hot or cold for your plants.

5.2 Future Work

- Setting up a substantial irrigation system for any type of land.
- To upgrade the infrastructure for vast agricultural fields.
- To enhance and add functionality to the water motors.
- Increasing the number of sensors to detect suspicious or thieving people at night.
- Including tools to trap dangerous insects in the field.

- Adding live assistance and instruction in smart agriculture to our offering.

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